

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Hamza****FIRST NAME: Abdelkarim****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What are the essential rules about schoolwork students learn when embarking on research work?**

- Good writing skills and ideas, use of features of Microsoft Word such as Styles and the Review tab, support to personal and specific writing, as well as showing arguments using facts as proof, give a student a strong base for academic writing.¹**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th Edition (Bangu: Euclid University, 2021), 12.

- Good writing skills only when they embark on research writing since, at the start, the focus is on the theoretical approach. The ideas use features of Microsoft Word.
 - Reading the introduction, the nature of dissertation research, potential synergy in dissertation research, and factors contributing to successful dissertation research.
 - Able to identify the dissertation components, recommended organization, and description of dissertation components.
2. **According to Kate L. Turabian's book, five critical objectives are essential to remember when embarking on a research endeavor.**
- Select a captivating and attainable topic, write an abstract, pinpoint a research problem, classify the project as pure or applied, and develop a preliminary hypothesis to steer the student's research efforts.
 - Select a captivating and attainable topic, and write an abstract to stimulate thought-provoking inquiries. The next consideration is for the student to pinpoint a research problem and classify the project as pure or applied.
 - The student is required to begin by formulating a significant question, discovering supported solutions, obtaining reliable data,**

constructing a persuasive argument, and refining the final product.²

- The student must develop a preliminary hypothesis to steer the student's research efforts, write an abstract, obtain reliable data, construct a persuasive argument, and refine the final product.

3. What are the components of dissertation research discussed in the guide for quantitative and qualitative dissertation research?

- Dissertation concept paper, abstract, methodology, dissertation prospectus, dissertation, and dissertation manuscript.
- Dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation, and dissertation manuscript.³**
- Dissertation abstract, acknowledgment, statement of the problem, literature review, methodology, data analysis and results, discussion, and conclusion.

² Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 44–65.

³ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 31.

- Dissertation abstract, acknowledgment, statement of the problem, literature review, methodology, data analysis and results, discussion, conclusion, and reference.
4. **An introduction sets the stage for the research study and directs the readers to the purpose and context of the dissertation. Which of the following gives the right order of a good introduction?**
- Introduction, problem statement, statement of the purpose, research questions, an overview of research design, rationale, and significance, the role of the researcher, researcher assumptions, definition of critical terminologies, and dissertation organization.⁴**
- Introduction, statement of the purpose, problem statement, research questions, an overview of research design, rationale, and significance, role of the researcher, researcher assumptions, definition of critical terminologies, and dissertation organization.
- Introduction, statement of the purpose, problem statement, research questions, an overview of research design, role of the researcher, researcher assumptions, rationale and significance, definition of key terminologies, and organization of the dissertation.

⁴ Sampson, 75.

- Introduction, problem statement, research questions, an overview of research design, rationale, and significance, statement of the purpose, the role of the researcher, researcher assumptions, organization of the dissertation, and definition of key terminologies.

- 5. **“To excel in research, a student must establish a well-defined research question and hypothesis while identifying trustworthy data sources.” Justify this statement.**

- Primary sources may serve as evidence to support hypotheses, while secondary sources do not always provide valuable insights into the findings of other researchers. Tertiary sources provide introductory overviews.

- Writing compels authors to articulate their opinions in the form of essays, substantiate their claims with supporting evidence, and maintain a respectful tone even when critiquing the work of others.

- The study demonstrates the necessity of thoroughly reviewing, revisiting, and rectifying our work to enhance its quality.

- Primary sources serve as evidence to support hypotheses, while secondary sources provide valuable insights into the findings of**

other researchers. Tertiary sources provide introductory overviews that can be beneficial for a wider audience.⁵

6. Plagiarism remains a non-ethical act. How can Educational institutions uphold ethical values and ensure students avoid plagiarism when writing a dissertation?

- Students need to copy and paste their sources, maintain a comprehensive record of references, select an appropriate citation style, and ensure that their bibliographic information is complete.
- Students need to evaluate the relevance and reliability of their sources, maintain a comprehensive record of references, select an appropriate citation style per their institution's guidelines, and ensure that their bibliographic information is complete.⁶**
- Students need to evaluate the relevance and reliability of their sources, maintain a comprehensive record of references, select an appropriate citation style, and ensure that their bibliographic information is complete.

⁵ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition*, 37.

⁶ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 7.

- Students need to evaluate the relevance and reliability of their sources, maintain a comprehensive record of references and use any appropriate citation style.

7. **An abstract summarizes a dissertation research paper. What components make a good abstract?**

- A brief introduction, the problem statement, the purpose of the study, the objective(s), the scope of the study, data sources, methodology, results, the key findings, conclusion, and recommendation.
- An introduction of the hypothesis, the problem statement, the purpose of the study, the objective(s), the scope of the study, methodology, results, the key findings, conclusion, and recommendation.
- A brief introduction of the research topic, the problem statement, the purpose of the study, the objective(s), the scope of the study, data sources, methodology, results, key findings, conclusion, and recommendation. It should be within the recommended word count.⁷**
- A research report should include an introduction, problem statement, purpose, objectives, scope, data sources, methodology, results, key

⁷ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition*, 1110–15.

findings, acknowledgments, conclusion, references, and recommendations.

8. **The following statements are correct on how numbers should be presented on a web page according to the WHO style guide.**

Which one is not?

- In publication, use figures for numbers in groups, figures and tables, and rangers and with units of measurement.
- Where a number consists of more than four digits, insert commas to separate them rather than a non-breaking space (control + shift + spacebar) before every set of three digits, counting from the right or left of the decimal point.⁸**
- In running text, give numbers zero to nine in words and 10 and higher numbers in figures. For large numbers combine numerals and words.
- In running text, give numbers zero to nine in words and 10 and higher numbers in figures. For large numbers combine numerals and words.

⁸ Turabian et al., 26–29.

9. What comprises precise sentence construction and writing understandable for the readers, as stated by the author Kate L. Turabian, when writing the final research draft?

- For clear writing, students should use a simple subject, separate words with a double space, highlight critical actions, and start with familiar information.
- For clear writing, a student should consider highlighting key actions, starting with familiar information, using proper verbs and pronouns and formal language, and steering clear of contractions.
- Use concise and concrete subjects, avoid single spaces, highlight actions, start with familiar info, use proper language, and avoid contractions.
- For a professional tone, use concise subjects, one space between words, emphasize actions, start with familiar details and formal language, and avoid contractions and errors.⁹**

10. Using ‘the English style guide,’ which of the following is correct regarding writing dates in the dissertation?

⁹ Turabian et al., 117.

- Dates in running text should always be given in their complete form, for instance, 28 April 2024, except for reference, which takes the short form of 28.04.2024. If the day of the week is included, for example, Friday, 28 April 2024, there is a comma after the day.
- Dates in running text should always be given in their complete form; 28 April 2024), except for reference, which takes the short form, which is 28.04.2024.
- Dates in running text should always be given in their complete form (day, month, year, for instance, 28 April 2024), except for reference, which takes a short form of 28.4.2024. If the day of the week is included, for example, Friday 28 April 2024, there is no comma after the day.¹⁰**
- Dates in running text should always be given in their short form 28.4.2024 (day.month.year) except for references which take the full form that is (day month year for instance 28 April 2024).

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *WHO Editorial Style Manual*, Second edition (Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 2013), 39.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Gulma Kabiru. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th Edition. Bangu: Euclid University, 2021.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

World Health Organization. *WHO Editorial Style Manual*. Second edition. Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.